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CONTENTS

Sr.No.	Author	Title of the Paper	Pg.No.	PDF
Indian Literature				
01	Aishvarya Partap & Prof. (Dr.) N. Padmasree	Social Reality and Change with Special Reference to Chetan Bhagat's Novels	01-13	PDF
02	Anita Goswami	Bharati Mukherjee's <i>The Holder of the World: An Odyssey</i>	14-20	PDF

		of Postcolonialism and Cultural Sensibility		
03	Anju Bala	Emergence of a New Woman: A Study of Shashi Deshpande's <i>A Matter of Time</i>	21-29	PDF
04	Arpita Dasgupta	Documenting Dalit History and Culture: An Alternative Reading of the <i>Ramayana</i>	30-33	PDF
05	Dr. Asha Madhavi Pagadala	Women as Victims of Power-Bound Society in <i>Silence! The Court is in Session</i>	34-41	PDF
06	Ashish Srivastava	Existentialism in Anita Desai's <i>Voices in the City</i>	42-47	PDF
07	Pandurang Bhagwan Daphal	Master-Servant Relationship in Arvind Adiga's <i>The White Tiger</i>	48-52	PDF
08	Debashis Biswas	Baul: In the Quest of <i>Moner Manush</i>	53-59	PDF
09	Nighat Fatima	Feminism in the Treatment of Kamala Das' Poetic Imagery	60-69	PDF
10	Dr. H. K. Jha	A Quest of Identity and Belongingness in Ruskin Bond's <i>The Room on the Roof</i>	70-83	PDF
11	Merlin Kumari. K	The Genesis of Indian Women in Literature	84-88	PDF
12	Mincy Mathew	A Road Not Taken: An Account of Dalit Experiences in Rohinton Mistry's <i>A</i>	89-94	PDF

		<i>Fine Balance</i>		
13	Miranda Taylor	Exploration of Identity in <i>The Satanic Verses</i> : How Binary Oppositions and Performativity Create Ontological Discourses	95-108	PDF
14	Mohua Ahiri	Crime, Punishment and Discipline in Amitav Ghosh's <i>Sea of Poppies</i>	109-114	PDF
15	Khundrakpam Nirupama & Dr. Sangeeta Laishram	Impact of Insurgency: Violence against Women in Manipur as Represented in Short Stories by Ningombam Sunita and Nepram Maya	115-118	PDF
16	Nishtha Mishra	Depiction of Key-features of Post-Colonialism through Selected Stories of Rudyard Kipling and R. K. Narayan	119-125	PDF
17	Dr. Vikas Jaoollkar & Pooja Bhatia	Culturally Ornate Stories of Tagore: <i>The Victory</i> and <i>Once there was a King</i>	126-129	PDF
18	Pooja	Indian Woman as Dalit and Diaspora: A Comparative Study of <i>Sangati</i> and <i>Coolie Woman</i>	130-137	PDF
19	A. Arulselesteen Prema & Dr. S. Kalamani	Double Marginalization of Dalit Women in Sivakami's <i>The Grip of Change</i> and <i>The Taming of Women</i>	138-145	PDF
20	Qaisar Bashir	Conflict Literature from Kashmir: A	146-153	PDF

		Study of <i>Curfewed Night</i> and <i>The Half Mother</i>		
21	Reetika Chanchal	Strangled Voices: A Study of Sexual Victimization in Mahesh Dattani's <i>Thirty Days in September</i>	154-160	PDF
22	Renu Gupta	Namita Gokhale's <i>Gods, Graves and Grandmother</i> as a Gender-Bender	161-166	PDF
23	Rinku Rani	Female Bonding: A Strategy of Survival in Shashi Deshpande's <i>The Binding Vine</i>	167-170	PDF
24	Rupali Chaturvedi	Identity Crises in Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's <i>Clothes</i>	171-174	PDF
25	Sachin Ketkar	Translating Darkness into Light: A Cultural Semiotics Reading of the Nation and the Region in <i>The White Tiger</i>	175-188	PDF
26	Sajad Ahmad Ganie & Dr. M. Madhavan	Gender: A Shame in Salman Rushdie's Novel <i>Shame</i>	189-192	PDF
27	Dr. Sanjay Kumar Dutta	Women Protagonists of Tagore: A Study of <i>Binodini</i>	193-199	PDF
28	Dr. Satya Paul	Asif Currimbhoy's <i>The Doldrummers</i> : An Analysis in Theme and Style	200-207	PDF
29	Shankar Lal Jhanjhnodia & Sanjit Mishra	The God that Failed: The Failure of Naxal Movement in Bani Basu's <i>The Enemy Within</i>	208-214	PDF

30	T. Staney Sherin	Gender Discrimination: An Outlook in Manju Kapur's <i>Difficult Daughters</i>	215-217	PDF
31	G. Stalin	Identity Crisis in Bharati Mukherjee's <i>Jasmine</i>	218-221	PDF
32	Victor Mukherjee	Exploring the Aesthetics of the 'Third Theatre': A Study of Badal Sircar's <i>Indian History Made Easy</i>	222-232	PDF
33	Ajay Kumar Yadav	Power and Violence in Vijay Tendulkar's <i>Ghashiram Kotwal</i>	233-243	PDF
34	Javaid Ahmad Tantry	Partition and Its Relevance in Contemporary Society	244-247	PDF
35	Enakshi Banerjee	Novel as History: A New Historical Reading of the Mughal harem in Kunal Basu's <i>The Miniaturist</i>	248-257	PDF
36	Ginni Rani	Ecocritical Reading of Jhumpa Lahiri's <i>The Lowland</i>	258-265	PDF
37	Dharma Chand Barai	Contemporary Indian Fiction in English: A Study of Postmodernist Narrative Strategy of Vikram Chandra's <i>Sacred Games</i>	266-274	PDF
American Literature				
01	Jasgeet Kaur	Individuals Trapped in the Labyrinth of Economy and Society: A Study of Khaled Hosseini's	275-281	PDF

		<i>And the Mountains Echoed</i>		
02	Sima Kumari	The Fusion of Intertextual Essence in Powers' <i>The Greek Slave</i> and Updike's <i>Before A Mirror</i>	282-291	PDF
03	Dr. Rakesh Kumar & Umara Shameen Butt	The Miserable and Scary Atmosphere of American Society in <i>No Country for Old Men</i>	292-297	PDF
04	Vijay Digambar Songire	Episodic Plots in Toni Morrison's <i>The Bluest Eye</i> , <i>Sula</i> and Alice Walker's <i>Meridian</i>	298-304	PDF
Critical Theory				
01	G. Anish S. Georshia	Indigenous Feminism on a Trajectory of Inclusive Feminism	305-315	PDF
02	Elise Simmons	Interactions between Character and Author	316-320	PDF
03	Okonkwo Gabriel Kosiso	The Creative Writer as a Creator-Continuum: A Caused Causer	321-328	PDF
04	Dr. Pratibha Kalani	Towards Spiritual Liberation	329-334	PDF
05	Dr. Rajib Bhaumik	Trans-Migratory State and Environmental Subject Signifiers in the Non-Synchronous Ethno-Environmental Context of North Bengal	416-423	PDF
Language & Linguistics				
01	Dr. Ch.Venkata	The Role of	335-340	PDF

	Ramani	Podcasts in Developing Language Skills of ESL Learners		
02	Dr. Divya Walia	Cinema and Social Media: Reinventing Classroom Teaching and Learning	341-345	PDF
03	Samson Mekonnen & Sewune Bora	An Investigation of Factors that Affect Students' Motivation towards English Language Learning: The Case of Wolaita Sodo University 1 st Year English Major Students	346-355	PDF
British Literature				
01	Dr. Ashok K. Saini	Sharp and Societal Milieu in Graham Swift's <i>Last Orders</i>	356-359	PDF
02	Dr. Sulekha Jadaun & Yogendra Pal Singh Solanki	Apartheid in African Countries as Reflected in Doris Lessing's <i>The Grass is Singing</i>	360-363	PDF
03	Shankar Vithoba Bhosale	The Exquisite Depiction of Romantic Suspense in the Novels of Mary Florence Stewart	424-429	PDF
Comparative Literature				
01	Akashjyoti Saikia & Dr. Dipendu Das	Representation of the American Dream in David Mamet's <i>Glengarry Glen Ross</i> (1982) and Kant's Views on Ethics and Morality: A Study	364-369	PDF
02	Madhusmita Pati	<i>The Hungry Tide</i>	370-375	PDF

		and <i>One Hundred Years of Solitude: Little Narrative vs the Grand Narrative</i>		
African Literature				
01	Sidney Shirly	Reductive Existence: A Study of J. M. Coetzee's <i>Life and Times of Michael K</i>	376-384	PDF
Canadian Literature				
01	Urmi Satyan	M G Vassanji's <i>The Book of Secrets: A Study of Engendered Culture of Colonized East Africa</i>	385-391	PDF
Irish Literature				
01	Shekhar Vispute	Depiction of Feministic Perspectives in G.B. Shaw's <i>Pygmalion</i>	392-399	PDF
02	Jamiel Ahmad	The (De)Centre Cannot Hold...: A Deconstructionist Study of W.B. Yeats' <i>The Second Coming</i>	410-415	PDF
French Literature				
01	Dhoop Singh Chahal	The Patience Stone: Voice of The 'Other'	400-404	PDF
Turkish Literature				
01	Dr. Qamar Talat & Seema Panjwani	Conflict, East Vs West and Inferiority Complex in Orhan Pamuk's <i>The Silent House</i>	405-409	PDF
P O E T R Y				
01	L. Ward Abel	Romulus	430	PDF
02	Anca Mihaela Bruma	The Autumn of Our Spring	431-433	PDF

03	Aparna B.	Today's Saddest Song	434-435	PDF
04	Diane Dehler	Salt & Sugar	436	PDF
05	Gregg Dotoli	Approach	437	PDF
06	Nandini Gupta	The Blessing in Disguise	438	PDF
07	Indunil Madhusankha	Extirpating the Darkness: In Search of the Light	439-440	PDF
08	Kuldipsinh D. Jadeja	Solitude	441	PDF
09	James Dickey	Government Man	442	PDF
10	Juan Pablo Duboué	Touch Me and You'll Burn	443	PDF
11	Julban Shefeek	Weeping Minds	444-445	PDF
12	Lana Bella	There Is Snow on the Distant Place	446	PDF
13	Helmi Ben Meriem	The Tree	447-448	PDF
14	Peter Cowlam	I'm So Fuci	449	PDF
15	Ruchi Chopra	Divine Truth	450-451	PDF
16	K. S. Subramanian	On the Tides of the New	452	PDF
17	Sunayna Pal	Alone	453	PDF
18	Shweta Sur	Old Wine in a New Bottle	454	PDF
19	Temitope Ogunsina	Drum	455	PDF
FICTION				
01	Krishnaveer Abhishek Challa	Down To Earth	456-459	PDF
02	Cyril Dabydeen	The Jamoon Tree	460-463	PDF
03	Subbaram Danda	Teenage Fears and Fantasies	464-467	PDF
04	Dr. Riyad Manqoush	Salwa and the Fake Husband	468-474	PDF
05	Dr. Vandana Singh	Awakening of Soul	475-483	PDF
BOOK REVIEW				
01	Gagan B Purohit	Two Minute's Silence by C.L. Khatri	484-487	PDF
02	Ishrat Jahan	Me Laxmi, Me	488-490	PDF

		Hijra: An Autobiography of Laxminarayan Tripathi Translated by R. Raj Rao and P. G. Joshi		
03	Dr.V. Jaisre	Difficult Daughters by Manju Kapur	491-492	PDF
04	Dr. Mukesh Yadav	Floating Haiku by Dr. Shalini Yadav	493-497	PDF
INTERVIEW				
01	Rakesh Kumar Mishra	Translated Interview of Uday Prakash by Rakesh Kumar Mishra	498-502	PDF